

Sustainable Workforce

Employee Questionnaire

Utrecht University

Middlesex University Business School

This project is being funded under the European Research Council's 7th Framework Programme, established by the European Commission

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Organisation: 110
Department: 1

Introduction

Thank you for participating in this study!

Many organisations invest in arrangements to improve their employees' lives, both at work and at home. We would like to know how you use these arrangements. We also have questions about your job and your household situation. You will need about 25 minutes to complete the questionnaire. All answers will be kept **in the strictest confidence**. Your employer will not be able to see your answers.

Your job

We start this questionnaire by asking you some general questions about your job at this organisation.

1 How many years have you been working for this organisation?

 _____ year(s)

If you have been working here for less than 1 year, please indicate the number of months.

 _____ month(s)

2 What is your occupation?

Please give a full description of your occupation, for example nurse at the intensive care, cashier at the bakery counter.

3 Do you have a supervisory position?

- Yes
- No

4 What kind of employment contract do you have?

- Permanent contract
- Fixed-term contract
- On-call contract
- Apprentice / trainee contract
- Sub-contracting
- Temporary employment agency contract
- Other (e.g., seasonal work, casual work, voluntary work)

 If you don't have a fixed-term contract, please continue to question 6.

5 When does your contract with this organisation end?

Month:

- January
- February
- March
- April
- May
- June
- July
- August
- September
- October
- November
- December

Year:

- 2015
- 2016
- 2017
- 2018
- 2019
- 2020
- 2021
- 2022
- 2023
- 2024
- 2025

6 How many hours a week are you contracted to work for this organisation?*Exclude any paid or unpaid overtime.*

- _____ hours a week
- I am not contracted on an hourly basis

7 How many hours a week do you actually work for this organisation?*Include paid or unpaid overtime, but not your commuting time.* _____ minutes

9 How do you usually travel to work?

Please refer to your main mode of transport and choose only one.

- On foot (you walk all the way)
- By bicycle (you cycle all the way)
- By motorcycle, scooter or moped
- By car, as the driver
- By car, as a passenger
- By bus, tram or tube
- By train

10 Do you receive a travel allowance?

- No, I do not receive a travel allowance
- Yes, it covers a small part of the cost
- Yes, it covers a large part of the cost
- Yes, it covers all or almost all of the cost

Background information

11 Are you male or female?

- Male
- Female

12 How old are you?

 _____ age

13 In which country were you born?

- UK
- Other, please specify: _____

14 What is the highest level of education that you have completed?

- Not completed primary education
- Primary education or first stage of basic education
- Lower level secondary education or second stage of basic education (GCSE or equivalent)
- Upper secondary education (AS, A LEVEL or GNVQ)
- Post-secondary, non-tertiary education (NVQ)
- First stage of tertiary education (BA or BSC)
- Second stage of tertiary education (MA or MSC)
- Doctoral degree (PhD)

Work flexibility

The following questions are about work flexibility arrangements in your organisation.

15 In the past 12 months, did you decide your own starting and finishing times?

For example, to start working at 7AM one day and at 9AM another day.

- Yes
- No

16 Does your organisation allow you to decide your own starting and finishing times?

For example, to start working at 7AM one day and at 9AM another day.

- Yes, it's formal policy (official policy)
- Yes, it's informal policy
- No
- Don't know

17 In the past 12 months, how often have you worked at home during normal working hours?

Exclude overtime.

- Never or almost never
- Less than 1 day a month
- Less than 1 day a week
- 1 day a week
- 2 days a week
- 3 days a week
- 4 or 5 days a week

18 Does the organisation allow you to work at home during normal working hours?

- Yes, it's formal policy (official policy)
- Yes, it's informal policy
- No
- Don't know

19 In the past 12 months, how often have you worked during your commute and counted it as working time?

- Never or almost never
- Less than 1 day a month
- Less than 1 day a week
- 1 day a week
- 2 days a week
- 3 days a week
- 4 or 5 days a week

20 Does your organisation allow you to count time spent working during your commute as working time?

- Yes, it's formal policy (official policy)
- Yes, it's informal policy
- No
- Don't know

21 In the past five years, have you switched from working full time to part time or vice versa?

- Yes, I switched from working full time to part time
- Yes, I switched from working part time to full time
- Yes, I both switched from working full time to part time and from working part time to full time
- No

22 Does your organisation offer the option to switch from full time to part time or vice versa?

- Yes, it's formal policy (official policy)
- Yes, it's informal policy
- No
- Don't know

Training

The following questions are about training and educational opportunities at your organisation.

23 In the past 12 months, have you been trained by a manager or co-worker?

- Yes, total number of days: _____
- No

 If you have not received training by a manager or co-worker, please continue to question 26.

24 How useful are the knowledge and skills you gained in this training for your current job?

- Very useful
- Useful
- Somewhat useful
- Not useful
- Not at all useful

25 How useful would the knowledge and skills you gained in this training be for a different organisation?

- Very useful
- Useful
- Somewhat useful
- Not useful
- Not at all useful

26 In the past 12 months, have you been trained by a professional instructor from outside your organisation?

- Yes, total number of days: _____
- No

 If you have not received training by a professional instructor from outside your organisation, please continue to question 29.

27 How useful are the knowledge and skills you gained in this training for your current job?

- Very useful
- Useful
- Somewhat useful
- Not useful
- Not at all useful

28 How useful would the knowledge and skills you gained in this training be for a different organisation?

- Very useful
- Useful
- Somewhat useful
- Not useful
- Not at all useful

29 In the past five years, have you been enrolled in an educational programme?

For example to obtain an MBA or a vocational qualification.

- Yes
- No

 If you did not take part in an educational programme, please continue to question 32.

30 Of the educational programme you have been enrolled in, what part of the cost was covered by your employer?

- All
- Most
- About half
- Some
- None

31 When you enrolled in this educational programme, did you have to sign an agreement stating that you would remain with your current employer for a specified period of time?

- Yes
- No

Health arrangements

We would now like to ask you some questions about arrangements in your organisation to help you live a healthy life.

32 Does your organisation offer catering or cafeteria menus based specifically on healthy nutrition?

For example a well-balanced selection of fruit, vegetables, fish, meat and low-fat products.

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

 If this arrangement does not exist in your organisation, please continue to question 34.

33 In the past 12 months, have you made use of these healthy menus?

- Yes
- No

34 Does your organisation offer sports facilities at work or a financial contribution towards a sports activity?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

 If this arrangement does not exist in your organisation, please continue to question 36.

35 In the past 12 months, have you made use of these sport facilities or contributions?

- Yes
- No

36 Does your organisation offer health-promoting ergonomic facilities?

For example, tools to optimize your workplace, such as an adjustable office chair.

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

👉 *If this arrangement does not exist in your organisation, please continue to question 38.*

37 In the past 12 months, have you made use of these ergonomic measures?

For example, tools to optimize your workplace, such as an adjustable office chair.

- Yes
- No

38 Does your organisation offer you the option of undergoing health checks to evaluate your current state of health?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

👉 *If this arrangement does not exist in your organisation, please continue to question 40.*

39 In the past 12 months, have you made use of these health checks?

- Yes
- No

40 How often does your work involve standing, walking or other physical activities?

- (Almost) always
- Often
- Regularly
- Sometimes
- (Almost) never

Leave and childcare arrangements

This section is about different types of leave and childcare arrangements in your organisation.

41 To your knowledge, does your organisation offer longer or better-paid leave arrangements than it is obliged to offer by law?

For example longer or better paid maternity, paternity or parental leave.

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

42 To your knowledge, does your organisation provide assistance with childcare?

For example financial assistance, childcare located at the workplace, or assistance with finding or arranging childcare.

- Yes
 No
 Don't know

43 The following questions relate to your own use of leave and childcare arrangements. Do you have any biological children younger than 18?

- Yes, age of your youngest child: _____ years
 No

 If you do not have any biological children younger than 18, continue to question 53.

44 Did you use any of the following leave arrangements in connection with the birth of your youngest child?

	No	Yes
Maternity leave / paternity leave	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Parental leave	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Did you take holiday to extend your leave period?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

 If you did not take maternity / paternity leave, continue to question 47.

45 How much maternity / paternity leave did you take?

- Less than what I was entitled to by law
 As much as I was entitled to by law
 More than I was entitled to by law

46 Was your maternity / paternity leave pay higher than the amount you were entitled to by law?

- Yes
 No

 If you did not take parental leave, continue to question 49.

47 How much parental leave did you take?

- Less than what I was entitled to by law
 As much as I was entitled to by law
 More than I was entitled to by law

48 Was your parental leave pay higher than the amount you were entitled to by law?

- Yes
 No

49 Did you have a partner in employment when your youngest child was born?

- Yes
 No

 If you did not have an employed partner when your youngest child was born, continue to question 51.

50 When your youngest child was born, did your partner (or ex-partner) use any of the following leave arrangements?

	Yes	No
Maternity leave / paternity leave	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Parental leave	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Did your partner take holiday to extend his / her leave period?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

 If your organisation doesn't provide assistance with childcare or if you don't know if it does, please continue to question 52.

51 Do you make use of childcare assistance offered by the organisation (or have you done so in the past)? *Multiple answers are possible.*

- Yes, financial assistance
 Yes, childcare at the workplace
 Yes, assistance finding or arranging childcare
 No, I don't use any childcare assistance offered by my organisation

52 Which other forms of childcare assistance do you use during working hours (or have you used in the past)? *Multiple answers are possible.*

- Unpaid childcare by relative or family friend
 Paid childcare by relative, family friend, or other non-professional
 Professional paid childcare
 Other
 None

53 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about your organisation?

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
My manager is understanding when I have to put my family first	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Employees who use work-family arrangements (e.g. leave policies, part-time work) are less serious about their careers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Employees are often expected to take work home at night or in the weekend	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Higher management encourages supervisors to be sensitive to employees' family concerns	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Employees are regularly expected to put their jobs before their families	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To turn down a promotion or transfer for family-related reasons will seriously hurt one's career progress in this organisation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My manager is very accommodating of family-friendly needs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Many employees are resentful when colleagues take extended leave to care for their newborns	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
To get ahead in this organisation, employees are expected to work overtime	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Age-related work arrangements

The following questions are about personnel policies aimed at employees who are 50 years or older.

 If you are younger than 50, please continue to question 62.

54 Does your organisation offer the following arrangements?

	Yes	No	Don't know
Additional leave from work or extra days off for older employees	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Specific training programmes for older employees	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

55 Have you used these arrangements in the past 12 months?*If the arrangement does not exist, please choose 'not applicable'.*

	Yes	No	Not applicable
Additional leave from work or extra days off for older employees	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Specific training programmes for older employees	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

56 Does your organisation offer the following arrangements?

	Yes	No	Don't know
Lighter workload in your current job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Semi-retirement	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

57 Have you used these arrangements since you turned 50?*If the arrangement does not exist, please choose 'not applicable'.*

	Yes	No	Not applicable
Lighter workload in your current job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Semi-retirement	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

58 Have you been promoted since you turned 50?

- Yes
 No

59 Have you had a reduction in your salary since you turned 50?

- Yes
 No

60 Leaving possible restrictions aside, at what age would you like to retire?

 _____ age

61 At what age do you think you can retire?

 _____ age

62 How old do you feel?

 _____ age

63 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
In my job I have never experienced unfavourable treatment because of my age	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My colleagues treat me less favourably because of my age	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My supervisor treats me less favourably than other workers because of my age	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

64 In your opinion, what is the youngest age that a person should be allowed to retire?

 _____ age

Work climate

The following questions are about the work climate within your organisation.

65 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about you and your colleagues?

In my department ...

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Everyone feels like part of the team	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We regularly ask one another for help or advice regarding work issues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We regularly give one another feedback	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We feel responsible for one another's work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We frequently see one another outside the office	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

66 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about you and your colleagues?

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
I often help my colleagues solve work-related problems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I often help new colleagues adjust to the work environment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I often volunteer to cover work assignments for colleagues when needed	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is most important to me to communicate and work together well with my colleagues	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

67 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about your organisation?

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
I am willing to go above and beyond the call of duty to help my organisation be successful	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I tell my friends that my organisation is a great place to work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am proud to tell others that I am part of this organisation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I really care about the future of this organisation	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

68 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about you and your supervisor?

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
My supervisor shows understanding if I have problems or wishes concerning my job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel appreciated by my supervisor	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My supervisor uses his/her influence to help me solve work-related problems	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My supervisor is friendly and approachable	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Work evaluation

The following questions are about how you experience your job.

69 The questions below concern the amount of freedom you have when carrying out your work in this organisation.

How often are you free to decide ...

	All the time	Most of the time	Sometimes	Mostly not	Never
The tasks you do in your job	<input type="radio"/>				
How you do your work	<input type="radio"/>				
The order in which you carry out tasks	<input type="radio"/>				
When you do your work	<input type="radio"/>				

70 How often does it happen that ...

	All the time	Most of the time	Sometimes	Mostly not	Never
Your job requires you to work fast	<input type="radio"/>				
Your job requires you to work very hard	<input type="radio"/>				
You feel that your job requires too much input from you	<input type="radio"/>				
Your job makes conflicting demands on you	<input type="radio"/>				

71 How often have you come across the following situations?

In the past three months ...

	Always	Often	Regularly	Sometimes	Seldom
I was able to plan my work so that I finished on time	<input type="radio"/>				
I kept in mind the work results I needed to achieve	<input type="radio"/>				
I was able to set priorities	<input type="radio"/>				
I was able to do my work efficiently	<input type="radio"/>				
I managed my time well	<input type="radio"/>				

72 And how often have you encountered the following situations?

In the past three months ...

	Always	Often	Regularly	Sometimes	Seldom
Without being told, I started on new tasks after finishing up my work	<input type="radio"/>				
I took on challenging new tasks when they were available	<input type="radio"/>				
I worked on keeping my work skills up-to-date	<input type="radio"/>				
I took on extra responsibilities	<input type="radio"/>				
I actively participated in meetings and/or consultations	<input type="radio"/>				

Well-being and job satisfaction

The following questions are about your sense of well-being.

73 All things considered, how satisfied are you with your current job?

Extremely dissatisfied										Extremely satisfied
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

74 How satisfied are you with the time you spend on paid work versus the time you spend on other parts of your life?

Extremely dissatisfied										Extremely satisfied
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

75 The following statements concern the influence your job has on your private life.

How often does it happen that ...

	Always	Often	Regularly	Sometimes	Never
You do not have the energy to engage in leisure activities with your family or friends because of your job?	<input type="radio"/>				
You have to work so hard that you do not have time for any of your hobbies?	<input type="radio"/>				
Your work obligations make it difficult for you to feel relaxed at home?	<input type="radio"/>				

76 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

My involvement in my work ...

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
Helps me to understand different viewpoints and this helps me be a better family member	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Helps me to gain knowledge and this helps me be a better family member	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Helps me to acquire skills and this helps me be a better family member	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

77 To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
I don't like to have to think about work while I'm at home	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I prefer to keep my working life at work	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I don't like work issues creeping into my home life	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I like to be able to leave my work behind when I go home	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

78 Can you indicate how often the following happens to you?

	Always	Often	Regularly	Sometimes	Never
I am under time pressure	<input type="radio"/>				
I wish I had more time for myself	<input type="radio"/>				
I feel I am under time pressure from others	<input type="radio"/>				
I cannot deal with important things properly due to a lack of time	<input type="radio"/>				

79 How is your health in general? Would you say it is ...

- Very good
- Good
- Fair
- Poor
- Very poor

Job outlook

The following questions are about your prospects within and outside this organisation.

80 Can you indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
I am likely to get a better job in this organisation in the next three years	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It would be easy for me to find a similar job if I had to leave my current one	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I worry about keeping my job	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

81 In the past six months, have you seriously looked for another job?

If you have been with your organisation for less than six months, consider the period since you started your job.

- Yes, within this organisation
- Yes, outside the organisation
- Yes, both within and outside the organisation
- No

Your household

The following questions are about your household, your partner and your children.

82 Do you currently live with a partner?

- Yes
- No

👉 If you do not live with a partner, please continue to question 89.

83 Is your partner male or female?

- Male
- Female

84 How old is your partner?

✎ _____ age

85 What is the highest level of education that your partner has completed?

- Not completed primary education
- Primary education or first stage of basic education
- Lower level secondary education or second stage of basic education (GCSE or equivalent)
- Upper secondary education (AS, A LEVEL or GNVQ)
- Post-secondary, non-tertiary education (NVQ)
- First stage of tertiary education (BA or BSC)
- Second stage of tertiary education (MA or MSC)
- Doctoral degree (PhD)

86 Which of the statements below best describes your partner's current situation?

- In paid work, on permanent contract
- In paid work, on a fixed-term contract
- In paid work, self-employed
- In education (not paid for by employer)
- Unemployed
- Permanently sick or disabled
- Retired
- Doing housework, looking after children or other persons
- Other

👉 If your partner is self-employed or not in paid work, please continue to question 89.

87 How many hours a week is your partner contracted to work?

Exclude any paid or unpaid overtime.

✎ _____ hours a week

88 Approximately how much time does it usually take for your partner to get to work?
Single journey only.

 _____ minutes

89 Do you have children living at **home**? If yes, how many?
Include adopted children, foster children, and stepchildren.

Yes, _____ number of children

No

 If you don't have any children living at home, please continue to question 93.

90 How old are the children living at home? Start with the **youngest** child.
If you have six or more children in the household, report the ages of the five youngest children.

Youngest child:

 _____ age

Housework and care responsibilities

These questions concern the time you spend on housework and caring for others.

91 On average, how much time do you spend on childcare every week?

For example: playing, changing diapers, taking children to clubs or events, helping with homework, etc.

 _____ hour(s) a week

 If you do not live with a partner, please continue to question 93.

92 On average, how much time does your partner spend on childcare every week?

For example: playing, changing diapers, taking children to clubs or events, helping with homework, etc.

 _____ hour(s) a week

93 On average, how much time do you spend on domestic duties every week?

For example: laundry, cleaning, preparing meals, grocery shopping, etc.

 _____ hour(s) a week

 If you do not live with a partner, please continue to question 95.

94 On average, how much time does your partner spend on domestic duties every week?

For example: laundry, cleaning, preparing meals, grocery shopping, etc.

 _____ hour(s) a week

95 In the past 12 months, have you cared for parents, other relatives or friends with health problems?

Yes, number of hours: _____ a week

No

 If you're younger than 50, please continue to question 98.

96 Do you have grandchildren?

Yes

No

 If you don't have any grandchildren please continue to question 98.

97 Have you cared for grandchildren in the past 12 months?

For example: playing, changing diapers, taking them to clubs or events, helping with homework etc.

Yes, number of hours: _____ a week

No

98 We would like to know what you think about housework and care responsibilities. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly agree	Agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly disagree
A man is just as capable of taking care of a baby as a woman	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It's unnatural for a man to do housework	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Man and wife should contribute equally to raising a child	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It's good for a young child if the father also contributes to taking care of him/her	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Final questions**99 What are your net monthly earnings from your main job at this organisation? Please refer to your average earnings in recent months.**

'Net monthly earnings' means what you have left every month after deducting national and local taxes and compulsory national insurance contributions.

Net monthly earnings in national currency: _____

I don't know exactly

 If you provided your exact monthly earnings, please continue to question 101.

100 If you don't know exactly what your net monthly earnings are, perhaps you can provide the approximate range. Which category best describes your net monthly earnings from your main job at this organisation?

If you don't know the exact category, please give an estimate.

- < 510 £
- 510 - 600 £
- 601 - 680 £
- 681 - 770 £
- 771 - 860 £
- 861 - 920 £
- 921 - 990 £
- 991 - 1070 £
- 1071 - 1150 £
- 1151 - 1240 £
- 1241 - 1320 £
- 1321 - 1420 £
- 1421 - 1510 £
- 1511 - 1630 £
- 1631 - 1760 £
- 1761 - 1910 £
- 1911 - 2060 £
- 2061 - 2330 £
- 2331 - 2610 £
- 2611 - 2880 £
- > 2880 £

101 If you combine income from all sources and all household members, which category best describes your household's total net monthly income?

If you don't know the exact category, please give an estimate.

- < 850 £
- 850 - 1200 £
- 1201 - 1410 £
- 1411 - 1590 £
- 1591 - 1830 £
- 1831 - 2160 £
- 2161 - 2560 £
- 2561 - 3100 £
- 3101 - 4470 £
- > 4470 £

102 What is your postal code?

- _____ postal code
- I don't want to provide this information

We very much appreciate your participation in the present survey!

In two years' time, we will repeat this survey in your organisation and we hope that you will participate again. To track changes in your work situation, we would like to be able to identify you while maintaining your anonymity. We can do this by encrypting the date of your birthday, so no one can identify you.

What is your birthday?

Day:

Month:

Of course, you may have left this organisation in two years' time. Even so, we are very interested in how your work situation has changed. We would like to ask for your email address so we can contact you. It will not be used for any other purpose and will not be disclosed to third parties.

What is your email address? If you don't want to provide your e-mail address, you can leave this field blank.

If you have any remarks, please note them below:

Experiment: How do you make decisions in your work?

Before you finish, we would like to ask you to take part in an interesting thought-experiment exploring how you make decisions in your work. It will only take a couple of minutes of your time and you can find it at the following pages. We hope that you will participate, but if you don't, please put the completed questionnaire in the envelope and put it in the sealed black box at your workplace.

Sustainable Workforce

Experiment A

Utrecht University

Middlesex University Business School

This project is being funded under the European Research Council's 7th Framework Programme, established by the European Commission

Info_UK@sustainableworkforce.eu
www.sustainableworkforce.eu

Organisation: 110
Department: 1

VignetteSetID (vignetteIDs): 12104 (10460, 10040, 10020, 10370)

Thank you for participating in the thought experiment!

On the following pages, you will be presented with four hypothetical scenarios, relating to a situation in which you and a partner are expecting a(nother) child. Please imagine that the following situation happens to you while you're employed in your current job, and express if and how much you would like to reduce your working hours in that situation. The situations refer to you and your partner - if you don't have a partner, please answer according to how you would respond if you did.

All answers will be kept strictly confidential.

Situation 1

You and your partner are expecting a child and you are considering whether one or both of you should reduce your working hours. Assume that you could afford to lose some income.

Furthermore, assume that there are no family members or friends available to help you with childcare.

- Your partner earns about the same as you do.
- The hourly rate charged for childcare is about the same as your hourly wage.

If you reduce your working hours:

- Most of your colleagues would approve.
- Your chances of getting promoted will not be affected.
- You will continue to do the same type of tasks, and your work will remain as enjoyable as it is now.

Questions

In this situation, would you reduce your contract to work fewer hours per week?

Yes, I would choose to work fewer hours per week than I work now, namely:

 _____ hours per week

No, I would not choose to work fewer hours per week than I work now

In this situation, how many hours per week would you like your partner to work?

 _____ hours per week

Situation 2

You and your partner are expecting a child and you are considering whether one or both of you should reduce your working hours. Assume that you could afford to lose some income. Furthermore, assume that there are no family members or friends available to help you with childcare.

- Your partner earns about the same as you do.
- The hourly rate charged for childcare is about the same as your hourly wage.

If you reduce your working hours:

- Most of your colleagues would disapprove.
- You will be less likely to get a promotion.
- You will have to give up some tasks you really enjoy.

Questions

In this situation, would you reduce your contract to work fewer hours per week?

Yes, I would choose to work fewer hours per week than I work now, namely:

 _____ hours per week

No, I would not choose to work fewer hours per week than I work now

In this situation, how many hours per week would you like your partner to work?

 _____ hours per week

Situation 3

You and your partner are expecting a child and you are considering whether one or both of you should reduce your working hours. Assume that you could afford to lose some income.

Furthermore, assume that there are no family members or friends available to help you with childcare.

- Your partner earns more than you do.
- The hourly rate charged for childcare is much lower than your hourly wage.

If you reduce your working hours:

- Most of your colleagues would disapprove.
- You will be less likely to get a promotion.
- You will have to give up some tasks you really enjoy.

Questions

In this situation, would you reduce your contract to work fewer hours per week?

Yes, I would choose to work fewer hours per week than I work now, namely:

 _____ hours per week

No, I would not choose to work fewer hours per week than I work now

In this situation, how many hours per week would you like your partner to work?

 _____ hours per week

Situation 4

You and your partner are expecting a child and you are considering whether one or both of you should reduce your working hours. Assume that you could afford to lose some income.

Furthermore, assume that there are no family members or friends available to help you with childcare.

- Your partner earns about the same as you do.
- The hourly rate charged for childcare is much lower than your hourly wage.

If you reduce your working hours:

- Most of your colleagues would disapprove.
- Your chances of getting promoted will not be affected.
- You will continue to do the same type of tasks, and your work will remain as enjoyable as it is now.

Questions

In this situation, would you reduce your contract to work fewer hours per week?

Yes, I would choose to work fewer hours per week than I work now, namely:

 _____ hours per week

No, I would not choose to work fewer hours per week than I work now

In this situation, how many hours per week would you like your partner to work?

 _____ hours per week

Lastly, could you please indicate how you experienced answering these questions?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
The situation described was realistic.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It was easy to relate the situations presented to myself.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The decisions were easy to make.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Please put the completed questionnaire in the enclosed envelope, and return it in the sealed black box at your workplace.

Thank you very much for completing the thought-experiment!